

Modeling solid materials in DEM using the micropolar theory

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Abstract The discrete element method (DEM) is a widely accepted method used in simulations of the powder sintering process, where the real object is replaced by a set of particles representing elastic-plastic material. Recently, this method has also been used to model solid materials. In this work, we present a local constitutive model for the determination of the interaction forces, which is based on micropolar theory. The model shows an elasto-viscoplastic behavior, thus an adaptation of the Johnson–Cook description of flow stress, which allows the analysis of solid materials subjected to high strain rates. The results of the DEM simulations received after calibration of the model parameters agree well with the experimental data from literature.

1 Introduction

The concept of the discrete element method was introduced by Cundall [1] in 1971 and was further developed by Cundall and Strack [2]. The increase in computing power of computers has contributed to the development of DEM in terms of both the complexity of the contact models used and the number of new phenomena analyzed using this method. The main area of application of the discrete element method is broadly understood geomechanics, where it is used to simulate soil behavior or analyze rock cracking [3, 4, 5, 6, 7]. The discrete element method is also a widely accepted method used in simulations of the powder sintering process [8, 9, 10, 11], and currently more and more

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attention is being paid to adapting this method to structural analysis, where the real object is replaced by a set of particles representing elastic plastic material [12, 13, 14, 15], including phenomena such as fracture [16] and crack propagation analysis [17].

The main difference between the discrete element method and the finite element method is the discretization of the object considered. In the case of DEM, a material is represented by an agglomeration of rigid or deformable particles that interact with each other by means of contact forces and moments. In turn, in FEM, the object considered is divided into finite elements that are interconnected at individual nodes. This is a significant difference because the lack of bonds between molecules in DEM allows for the analysis of problems related, e.g. with the formation of discontinuities in the material, or problems in which significant plastic deformations occur. In addition, the need to store large stiffness matrices, which are the basis for implicit integration, disappears. In general, discrete elements can have any shape [18], however, due to the simplicity in formulating the mathematical description and efficiency of the calculations, spherical particles [19] are most often used.

In this work, we present a local constitutive model for the determination of interaction forces, which is based on micropolar theory [20, 21]. The model shows an elasto-viscoplastic behavior, thus an adaptation of the Johnson-Cook description of flow stress [22], which allows the analysis of solid materials subjected to high strain rates. The model is validated in the analysis of uniaxial tensile tests of an aluminum alloy sample. The tests considered two constant values of strain rate and two values of discrete element radius, additionally the consideration of classical Cauchy theory is presented by neglecting the coupled stress component. The results of the DEM simulations received after calibration of the model parameters agree well with the experimental data provided by [23].

2 Formulation of the thermo-elasto-viscoplastic contact model

2.1 Short introduction to DEM basics

As mentioned above, the interaction of the particles causes the contact force vector \mathbf{F} (Fig. 1). As a result of the interaction, in addition to the translational movement, there is also a rotational movement of the bodies, where the point c is treated as a temporary center of rotation. The angle of rotation is determined by the moment vector \mathbf{M} , which is related to the resulting force \mathbf{F} . The reliability of this method depends mainly on the proper definition of the contact model, which can be seen as a micromechanical model of the material. However, it is not trivial to define material properties on the micro

Fig. 1 Schematic illustration of the particle-particle interaction with force decomposition on normal \mathbf{F}_N and tangential \mathbf{F}_T direction.

scale, and they are usually not related to macro properties. Therefore, to identify these parameters, the constitutive model used must be calibrated.

The discrete element method was developed to analyze the dynamic interaction of a set of particles in contact with each other. In general, these particles are treated as ideally rigid bodies that have six degrees of freedom. The interaction forces between particles \mathbf{F} are modeled using a system of fictitious springs with stiffness k_N, k_T , and for more complex models, additional elements are used in the form of dampers c_N or friction pairs μ_T are used. The resultant interaction force is the sum of the normal and tangential components

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}_N + \mathbf{F}_T = F_N \mathbf{n} + \mathbf{F}_T \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{n} is the unit normal vector of the plane located at the point of contact and pointing outward from the discrete element

$$\mathbf{n} = \frac{\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i}{|\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i|}. \quad (2)$$

Then the resultant force is used to calculate the position and orientation of a given discrete element, using Newton–Euler dynamic equilibrium equations

$$\begin{aligned} m_i \ddot{\mathbf{x}}_i &= \mathbf{F}_i = \sum_{n=1}^{N_i^c} \mathbf{F}_n \\ I_i \ddot{\phi}_i &= \mathbf{M}_i = \sum_{n=1}^{N_i^c} \mathbf{r}_{ci} \times \mathbf{F}_n \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where N_i^c is the number of interactions of i -th element, and \mathbf{r}_{ci} is the vector connecting the center of mass of the particle with the contact point c (Fig. 1). While integrating the first equation of motion gives us information about the position of the element, integrating the second equation allows us to deter-

mine the rotation of the local coordinate system in relation to the reference system.

At the moment of interaction, the initial length l_0 of the fictitious element in the form of a spring, contained between the particles, is defined as

$$l_0 = |\mathbf{x}_j^0 - \mathbf{x}_i^0| \quad (4)$$

this length is treated as a reference value used to calculate other geometric relationships.

2.2 DEM interaction force model based on micropolar theory

At the beginning of this section, we recall the basic constitutive relations that describe Cosserat continua. The modified versions of these relations, where the strain tensor and the curvature tensor are decomposed into a symmetric () and non-symmetric <> part [21], are presented

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{ij} &= 2\mu\varepsilon_{(ij)} + 2v\varepsilon_{<ij>} + (\lambda\varepsilon_{kk} - \alpha'\theta) \delta_{ij} \\ \mu_{ij} &= 2\gamma\kappa_{(ij)} + 2\eta\kappa_{<ij>} + \mathcal{T}\kappa_{kk}\delta_{ij} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where σ_{ij}, μ_{ij} are the stress and coupled stress tensors respectively, μ, λ are the Lamé constants, v, γ, η are new elastic constants, α' and $\mathcal{T} = 0$ are thermomechanical parameters, and δ_{ij} is a Kronecker delta. Since in (5) the symmetric and non-symmetric parts of these tensors were used, we recall the description of the strain tensors

$$\varepsilon_{(ij)} = \frac{1}{2}(u_{j,i} + u_{i,j}), \quad \varepsilon_{<ij>} = \frac{1}{2}(u_{j,i} - u_{i,j}) - \varepsilon_{ijk} \omega_k \quad (6)$$

as well as the curvature tensors

$$\kappa_{(ij)} = \frac{1}{2}(\omega_{j,i} + \omega_{i,j}), \quad \kappa_{<ij>} = \frac{1}{2}(\omega_{j,i} - \omega_{i,j}). \quad (7)$$

In the present model, the description is limited to a simplified theory of Cosserats' brothers known as the pseudo-Cosserat continuum. This theory assumed that $\varepsilon_{<ij>} = \frac{1}{2}(u_{j,i} - u_{i,j}) - \varepsilon_{ijk} \omega_k = 0$, which leads to the relation

$$\omega_k = \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_{klm} u_{m,l} \quad (8)$$

associating the rotation with the displacement field. Although the non-symmetric part of the strain tensor is equal to zero, the corresponding non-symmetric part of the stress tensor $\sigma_{<ij>} = 2v\varepsilon_{<ij>}$ does not vanish and can be determined from the equilibrium equation of momentum conservation

$$\epsilon_{ijk} \sigma_{jk} + \mu_{ji,j} = 0. \quad (9)$$

Taking into account the particle-particle interaction in the discrete element

Fig. 2 Illustration of the displacement plane Π determined by the vectors \mathbf{n} and \mathbf{e} a), geometry of the virtual volume element V' b).

method, the forces and the corresponding moment are located in the plane Π determined by vectors \mathbf{n} and \mathbf{e} (Fig. 2a) in each time step, where

$$\mathbf{e} = \frac{\mathbf{u}_T}{|\mathbf{u}_T|}. \quad (10)$$

We assumed that the virtual volume element (Fig. 2b) is subjected to deformation by prescribed displacements \mathbf{u}_N and \mathbf{u}_T in this particular plane. We can rewrite those displacements as $\mathbf{u}_N = \mathbf{n}u_N$ and $\mathbf{u}_T = \mathbf{e}u_T$, and change the indices to $u_1 = u_N, u_2 = u_T$. Now we consider the deformation of the virtual element in a plane as a combination of pure shear deformation and rigid rotation, where

$$\omega_3 = \frac{1}{2}u_{2,1} = \frac{u_2}{2l_0}. \quad (11)$$

This results in definitions of displacement and rotation vectors as follows

$$\mathbf{u} = \{u_1, u_2, 0\}^T, \quad \boldsymbol{\omega} = \{0, 0, \omega_3\}^T. \quad (12)$$

Based on the description widely used to determine the strains in DEM models, we can determine the corresponding strain components as

$$\epsilon_{11} = \frac{u_1}{l_0}, \quad \epsilon_{12} = \epsilon_{21} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{u_2}{l_0} \quad (13)$$

then the curvature components

$$\begin{aligned}
 \kappa_{(13)} &= \frac{1}{2}(\omega_{3,1} + \underbrace{\omega_{1,3}}_{=0}) = \frac{1}{2}\kappa_{13} = \frac{1}{4}u_{2,11} \\
 \kappa_{\langle 13 \rangle} &= \frac{1}{2}(\omega_{3,1} - \underbrace{\omega_{1,3}}_{=0}) = \frac{1}{2}\kappa_{13} = \frac{1}{4}u_{2,11} \\
 \kappa_{(23)} &= \frac{1}{2}(\omega_{3,2} + \underbrace{\omega_{2,3}}_{=0}) = \frac{1}{2}\kappa_{23} = \frac{1}{4}u_{2,12} \\
 \kappa_{\langle 23 \rangle} &= \frac{1}{2}(\omega_{3,2} - \underbrace{\omega_{2,3}}_{=0}) = \frac{1}{2}\kappa_{23} = \frac{1}{4}u_{2,12}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

The use of such a deformation, which is the same as the widely used approach in the DEM method, makes it impossible to obtain higher-order derivatives required in the current model. For this reason, a shape function was introduced in the form that describes the deformation of the virtual element, depending on the relative displacement of the centers of the particles. It was assumed that the surfaces perpendicular to the direction of the x'_1 axis do not subject to warp (Fig. 3). The third-degree polynomial $\mathcal{N}(x'_1) =$

Fig. 3 A scheme illustrating the relative displacement of a discrete element with the normal \mathbf{u}_N and tangent \mathbf{u}_T components of the displacement vector in a local coordinate system x'_1, x'_2 .

$c_1 + c_2x'_1 + c_3x'^2_1 + c_4x'^3_1$ was used to determine the form of the function, where x'_1 is the coordinate in the local coordinate system, where, for simplicity, the origin of the system is located in the center of the particle i . The assumed degree of the polynomial guarantees the differentiability of the function in the required range determined by the constitutive equations of the micropolar medium. In order to determine the constants occurring in the polynomial, boundary conditions in the form of

$$\mathcal{N}(x'_1)|_{x'_1=0} = 0, \quad \mathcal{N}(x'_1)|_{x'_1=l_0} = u_2 \tag{15}$$

while for the first derivative $d\mathcal{N}(x'_1)/dx'_1 = c_2 + 2c_3x'_1 + 3c_4x'^2_1$, due to the kinematic condition (8) adopted

$$\left. \frac{d\mathcal{N}(x'_1)}{dx'_1} \right|_{x'_1=0} = \frac{u_2}{2l_0}, \quad \left. \frac{d\mathcal{N}(x'_1)}{dx'_1} \right|_{x'_1=l_0} = \frac{u_2}{2l_0}. \quad (16)$$

Finally, the interpolation function will take the form of

$$\mathcal{N}(x'_1) = \frac{1}{2l_0}x'_1 + \frac{3}{2l_0^2}x'^2_1 - \frac{1}{l_0^3}x'^3_1. \quad (17)$$

Figure 4 shows a graphical interpretation of the function (17) and its derivatives, where the $u_2 \in \{0, 1\}$ range was assumed to illustrate the dependence on the displacement of the discrete element. The reference length was assumed as the unit $l_0 = 1$. Now, we can compute the curvature components and their derivatives, where the quantity κ_{kk} vanishes due to $\text{div}\boldsymbol{\omega} = 0$. Since \mathcal{N} is a function of only x'_1 , the second rank tensor of $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ will be zero

Fig. 4 The influence of the "nodal" displacement u_2 of the particle on the distribution of: displacements a), strains b) and curvature c) along the x'_1 coordinate of the virtual element V' .

$$\kappa_{13} = \frac{1}{2}u_{2,11} = -\frac{3}{2l_0^2}u_2, \quad \kappa_{23} = \frac{1}{2}u_{2,12} = 0. \quad (18)$$

Determining the moment and force of two particles that contact each other requires an analysis of the state of stress in the plane of interaction Π . Due to the deformation, a stress state will be created in the virtual element, for which it is assumed that the surfaces $x'_3 = \pm r$ are stress-free, therefore $\sigma_{13} = \sigma_{23} = \sigma_{31} = \sigma_{32} = \sigma_{33} = \mu_{31} = \mu_{32} = \mu_{33} = 0$. It can be seen that in the considered element, the stress state is reduced to a plane problem, and due to the kinematics of the system, the coupled stress components μ_{11} , μ_{12} and the stress σ_{22} are equal to zero. Since the nonsymmetric strain components are zero $\varepsilon_{\langle 12 \rangle} = \varepsilon_{\langle 21 \rangle} = 0$, therefore $\varepsilon_{12} = \varepsilon_{(12)}$ and $\varepsilon_{21} = \varepsilon_{(21)}$

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{11} &= 2\mu\varepsilon_{11} + \frac{\nu E}{1+\nu}\varepsilon_{11} - E\alpha\theta = E\left(\frac{u_1}{l_0} - \alpha\theta\right) \\ \sigma_{12} &= 2\mu\varepsilon_{12} - \frac{1}{4}\xi(\kappa_{13,1} + \kappa_{23,2}) = \mu\frac{u_2}{l_0} + \frac{3}{2}\xi\frac{u_2}{l_0^3} \\ \sigma_{21} &= 2\mu\varepsilon_{21} + \frac{1}{4}\xi(\kappa_{13,1} + \kappa_{23,2}) = \mu\frac{u_2}{l_0} - \frac{3}{2}\xi\frac{u_2}{l_0^3} \\ \mu_{13} &= \xi\kappa_{13} = -\frac{3}{2}\xi\frac{u_2}{l_0^2} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

The constant ξ is a combination of previous constants $\gamma + \eta$, and was introduced after simple manipulations in equation (5).

2.3 Visco-plasticity

During the material deformation process, which is accompanied by high deformation rates and high temperature, in addition to the plastic flow of the material, there are also viscous phenomena, that is, creep or relaxation of the material. The system of constitutive equations (19) can be represented as in [24] by vectors containing only non-zero components of the corresponding tensors. To maintain the appropriate dimension of a given quantity, the characteristic length ℓ was introduced. We will write the stress and the strain column vectors as

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \{\sigma_{11}, \sigma_{12}, \sigma_{21}, \mu_{13}/\ell\}^T, \quad \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = \{\varepsilon_{11}, \varepsilon_{12}, \varepsilon_{21}, \kappa_{13}\ell\}^T \quad (20)$$

and the corresponding stiffness matrix in the form

$$\widehat{\mathbf{C}} = \begin{bmatrix} 2\mu + \lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2\mu & 0 & -\frac{1}{4}\xi \\ 0 & 0 & 2\mu & \frac{1}{4}\xi \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{4}\xi & \frac{1}{4}\xi & \xi \end{bmatrix}. \quad (21)$$

As in the classical formulation of plasticity, the strain tensor and the curvature tensor can be represented as the sum of the elastic and plastic parts [25, 26], and the strains resulting from the thermal effect. Whereas the ε_{11} strain in the discrete element method is calculated based on the penetration value of the two spheres (and not incrementally), the incremental Hooke's law will be expressed by the formula

$$\widehat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_{r+1} = \widehat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_{r+1}^{\text{trial}} - \Delta\widehat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^{\text{p}} - \Delta\widehat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^{\theta} = \widehat{\mathbf{C}} : (\widehat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{r+1} - \widehat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{r+1}^{\text{p}} - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{r+1}^{\theta}) \quad (22)$$

The algorithm was built based on the forward Euler scheme and the use of the cutting plane method [27]. The return mapping algorithm assumes an increase in elastic strain in step $r + 1$, which, using the constitutive relation, results in trial stress $\widehat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^{\text{trial}}$. For the stress calculated in this way, the yield condition $F(\widehat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}, R) \leq 0$ is checked, if the criterion is met, then the stress vector is inside the yield surface and the test stress is the stress at the end of step $r + 1$, that is, $\widehat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_{r+1} = \widehat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_{r+1}^{\text{trial}}$. Otherwise, when $F(\widehat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}, R) > 0$ a viscoplastic corrector is required to bring the stress vector to the current yield surface. This procedure involves calculating the increment of the plastic part of the strain tensor $\Delta\widehat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{\text{p}}$.

The yield function, assuming only isotropic hardening, can be represented as

$$F_{r+1}^{\text{v}} = f_{r+1} - \sigma_{y,r+1} \left(1 + C \ln \frac{\Delta\lambda_{r+1}}{\dot{p}_0 \Delta t_{r+1}} \right) \left(1 - \left[\frac{T_{r+1} - T_{\text{ref}}}{T_{\text{melt}} - T_{\text{ref}}} \right]^m \right) \quad (23)$$

where the flow stress is described by the Johnson–Cook model [22]. Expanding the plasticity function in a Taylor series

$$F_{r+1}^{i+1} = F_{r+1}^i + \frac{\partial F}{\partial \widehat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_{r+1}} \delta \widehat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_{r+1} + \frac{\partial F}{\partial \sigma_{y,r+1}} \delta \sigma_{y,r+1} + \frac{\partial F}{\partial v_{\text{p},r+1}} \delta v_{\text{p},r+1} = 0 \quad (24)$$

where $\delta \widehat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$, $\delta \sigma_y$ and δv_p are increments of individual variables in the next iteration step i . Considering that the internal state variable $\dot{p} = \dot{\lambda} = \frac{\Delta\lambda}{\Delta t}$ controls the effect of viscoplasticity $v_p(\dot{p})$ will take the form

$$v_p(\Delta\lambda_{r+1}) = \left(1 + C \ln \frac{\Delta\lambda_{r+1}}{\dot{p}_0 \Delta t_{r+1}} \right) \quad (25)$$

while the state variable responsible for thermal effects will be written as a function

$$\Gamma_p(T_r) = \left(1 - \left[\frac{T_r - T_{\text{ref}}}{T_{\text{melt}} - T_{\text{ref}}}\right]^m\right). \quad (26)$$

Finally, after differentiation, equation (24) will take the form

$$F_{r+1}^{i+1} = F_{r+1}^i - \frac{\partial F}{\partial \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_{r+1}} \hat{\mathbf{C}} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_{r+1}} \delta \lambda_{r+1}^{i+1} - v_{p,r+1} \Gamma_{p,r} H_{R,r+1} \delta \lambda_{r+1}^{i+1} - \sigma_{y,r+1} \Gamma_{p,r} \frac{\partial v_{p,r+1}}{\partial \lambda_{r+1}} \delta \lambda_{r+1}^{i+1}. \quad (27)$$

Using the substitution previously presented for $\dot{\lambda}$, the increase in the plasticity multiplier in the next iteration step will be expressed in the form

$$\delta \lambda_{r+1}^{i+1} = \frac{f_{r+1}^i}{\frac{\partial F}{\partial \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_{r+1}} \hat{\mathbf{C}} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_{r+1}} + v_{p,r+1} \Gamma_{p,r} H_{R,r+1} + \sigma_{y,r+1} \Gamma_{p,r} \frac{\partial v_{p,r+1}}{\partial \Delta \lambda_{r+1}}} \quad (28)$$

where

$$\frac{\partial v_p(\Delta \lambda_{r+1})}{\partial \Delta \lambda} = \frac{C}{\Delta \lambda_{r+1}} \quad (29)$$

$$H_{R,r+1} = \frac{dR_{r+1}}{dp_{r+1}} = Bn \lambda_{r+1}^{n-1} \quad (30)$$

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}} \hat{\mathbf{C}} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}} = \frac{3}{2J_2} \left\{ \frac{2}{9} E \sigma_{11}^2 + \mu \left(\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{21}^2 + \frac{1}{8\ell^2 l_0} \xi (\sigma_{21} - \sigma_{12}) \mu_{13} \right) + \frac{1}{2\ell} \xi \mu_{13}^2 \right\}. \quad (31)$$

Within each iterative step, the thermodynamic forces are updated with respect to the current state of stress along with the calculation of a new value for the yield function

$$F_{r+1}^{v,i+1} = f_{r+1}^{i+1} - \sigma_{y,r+1}^{i+1} \left(1 + C \ln \frac{\Delta \lambda_{r+1}^{i+1}}{\dot{p}_0 \Delta t_{r+1}}\right) \left(1 - \left[\frac{T_r - T_{\text{ref}}}{T_{\text{melt}} - T_{\text{ref}}}\right]^m\right) \quad (32)$$

and checking the convergence of the solution

$$\left| \frac{F^v(\Delta \lambda_{r+1}^{i+1})}{\sigma_{y,r+1} v_p \Gamma_p} \right| \leq \text{TOL} \quad (33)$$

for a fixed tolerance value. If this value is within the tolerance range, the iterative procedure is stopped, and the individual model parameters are updated.

It should be taken into account that not all the energy associated with plastic deformation is dissipated in the form of thermal energy. A certain part of it is used for structural changes that take place in the material, and hence

$$\mathfrak{D}^P = \chi \sigma \dot{\varepsilon}^P = \chi \sigma_{\text{eq}} \dot{p} \quad (34)$$

where the Taylor-Quinney coefficient χ is usually 0.9.

3 Model verification

In this section, the verification of the model presented is discussed based on stress-strain plots. This is done by comparing the plots from the DEM simulations and the analytical model based on the parameters of the J-C model obtained from the experiment.

3.1 Simulation set-up

In the current study, the introduced thermo-elasto-viscoplastic model was implemented in open-source YADE software [28] and validated using an analytical solution based on the parameters presented in [23]. The numerical dynamic tensile tests were carried out on an axisymmetric sample (Fig. 5a) with dimensions of: $d_1 = 20$ mm, $d_2 = 10$ mm, $R = 10$ mm, $L_1 = 30$ mm, $L_2 = 15$ mm and $L_3 = 80$ mm. To analyze the influence of the discrete element size on the results, two cases of sample geometry discretization were checked. In the first case, the radius of the spherical elements was 1 mm (Fig. 5b) and in the second case $r = 0.75$ mm (Fig. 5c). The number of particles in the case of $r = 1$ mm was 1842 and for $r = 0.75$ was 4873. Performed DEM simulations do not take into account temperature softening at this moment. The parameters of the material are presented in Table 1. Some of the material properties were not calibrated, including Young's modulus $E = 70$ GPa, Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.3$, material density $\rho = 2710$ kg/m³ and reference strain rate $\dot{\varepsilon}_{\text{ref}} = 0.0001$ 1/s. Additional parameters that we introduced in the TEVP model and are related to coupled stresses were the characteristic length $\ell = 0.025$ mm and the elastic constant $\xi = Er^2/3$. The iterative parameters of the return mapping algorithm were: TOL = $1 \cdot 10^{-1}$ and MXITER = 100.

Table 1 Material properties of the 6082-T6 aluminum alloy used in the simulations.

Parameter	Value from literature [23]	Calibrated value	Unit
A	277.33	178.67	MPa
B	307.93	25.73	MPa
n	0.69	0.43	-
C	0.0032	$5 \cdot 10^{-10}$	-

Fig. 5 Sample geometry used in DEM simulations a), discretized by spherical elements with radius value of 1 mm b) and 0.75 mm c).

To illustrate the sensitivity of the model to dynamic behavior, two constant strain rates were investigated: 1 and 10000 s^{-1} .

3.2 Results and discussion

Figure 6a shows the comparison of the analytical solution with the stress-strain curve from DEM simulation where the initial values of the material parameters were used. There is no apparent correlation with the experimental model. The discrete element method shows a yield strength about twice as high as in reality. In addition, the observable strengthening effect is much greater than in the case of the analytical model. This is a disadvantage of the DEM formulation, where a calibration of the model must be performed in the initial step, before the right simulation [29]. In this work, we use a trial-and-error method for the calibration of the model material parameters. Due to the specific formulation of this method, the DEM model shows high sensitivity to material parameters. The initial yield strength that describes the parameter A was calibrated first, but, unlike the analytical model, the DEM model does not exhibit ideal plastic flow (Fig. 6b). This could be explained by the dynamic behavior of the material. During tension, we can observe the stress wave propagating along the sample (Fig. 7). This effect is different from the analytical model, which describes the material in terms of a material point. As a result of the material response, the effect of clear non-linearity in the initial

Fig. 6 Comparison of a non-calibrated model with an analytic solution a) and calibration of the parameters of the J-C model used in the DEM model b).

range of plastic flow is visible. Also visible is the effect of stress gradation, which is not observed in the analytical model. Calibration of the parameters B and n , taking into account the value of A , results in an increase in stress in relation to strain.

Appropriate calibration of the DEM model parameters results in a proper response to the applied load in the form of the strain rate. At speeds of 1 s^{-1} and 10000 s^{-1} , the DEM model shows good accuracy compared to the analytical model (Fig. 8a). A difference in the plastic behavior of the material is also observable, which in the case of the discrete element method shows a certain non-linearity in determining the yield point. It is also noticeable depending on the value of the strain rate. The graphic shows the influence of the size of the discrete element on the stress value during the sample loading process. Reducing the radius of the particles results in an increase in yield strength and associated stress. This effect can be related to the decrease in the stress value with an equivalent strain value due to a decrease in particle size. Changing the model by excluding coupled stresses, in the case of an analysis with a 1 mm element size, results in an increase in stresses and yield strength. This allows us to conclude that the coupled stresses result in an increase in the effective stress and therefore in a decrease in the yield strength of the material.

4 Concluding remarks

In this work we have presented a new local constitutive model for the DEM obtained by using micropolar theory. The model takes into account not only the elasticity but also the viscoplastic behavior of the material, where the Johnson–Cook model was adopted. The results obtained from the uniaxial

Fig. 7 Stress map of σ_{22} in the sample analyzed at a particular time during the loading process.

tensile tests confirm that the model correctly reproduces the mechanism of strain rate sensitivity.

Fig. 8 Response of the material to strain rates of 1 s^{-1} and 10000 s^{-1} a), stress-strain relation depending on the size of the element and the existence of coupled stress b).

These findings reinforce the potential use of the TEVP model in analysis of metallic materials subjected to high strain rates. The applicability of DEM to the linear and non-linear analysis of ductile material has been proved.

There is still a need to understand the sensitivity of the model to initial material parameters and the influence of particle size on stress response. The work on those problems is in progress and the results will be published in a succeeding paper.

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References

1. Cundal PA (1971) A computer model for simulating progressive, large-scale movements in blocky rock systems. Synopsium Soc. Internat Mécanique des Roches 2–8
2. Cundal PA, Strack ODL (1979) A discrete numerical method for granular assemblies. Geotechnique 29:47–65
3. Oñate E, Zárata F, Miquel J, Santasusana M, Celigueta MA, Arrufat F, Gandikota R, Valiullin K, Ring L (2015) A local constitutive model for the discrete element method. Application to geomaterials and concrete. Computational Particle Mechanics 2(2):139–160
4. Rojek J (2014) Discrete element thermomechanical modelling of rock cutting with valuation of tool wear. Computational Particle Mechanics 1(1):71–84
5. He Y, Zhang J, Andriollo T, Hattel J, Zhao W (2019) Investigation of the elastoplastic and fracture behavior of solid materials considering microstructural anisotropy: A discrete element modeling study. Computational Materials Science 170

6. Fathipour-Azar H, Wang J, Jalali SME, Torabi SR (2020) Numerical modeling of geomaterial fracture using a cohesive crack model in grain-based DEM. *Computational Particle Mechanics* 7(4):645–654
7. Joulin C, Xiang J, Latham JP (2020) A novel thermo-mechanical coupling approach for thermal fracturing of rocks in the three-dimensional FDEM. *Computational Particle Mechanics* 7(5):935–946
8. Martin CL, Schneider LCR, Olmos L, Bouvard D (2006) Discrete element modeling of metallic powder sintering. *Scripta Materialia* 55(5):425–428
9. Nosewicz S, Rojek J, Pietrzak K, Chmielewski M (2013) Viscoelastic discrete element model of powder sintering. *Powder Technology* 246:157–168
10. Rojek J, Nosewicz S, Pietrzak K, Chmielewski M (2013) Simulation of powder sintering using a discrete element model. *Acta Mechanica et Automatica* 7(3):175–179
11. Rojek J, Nosewicz S, Maździarz M, Kowalczyk P, Wawrzyk K, Lumelskyj D (2017) Modeling of a Sintering Process at Various Scales. *Procedia Engineering* 177:263–270
12. André D, Iordanoff I, Charles JL, Néauport J (2012) Discrete element method to simulate continuous material by using the cohesive beam model. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* 213-216:113–125
13. Nguyen VDX, Tieu AK, André D, Su L, Zhu H (2021) Discrete element method using cohesive plastic beam for modeling elasto-plastic deformation of ductile materials. *Computational Particle Mechanics* 8:437–457
14. Lei Z, Bradley CR, Munjiza A, Rougier E, Euser B (2020) A novel framework for elastoplastic behaviour of anisotropic solids. *Computational Particle Mechanics* 7(5):823–838
15. Jebahi M, André D, Terreros I, Iordanoff I (2015) Discrete element method to model 3D continuous materials. ISTE, London
16. Kozicki J, Tejchman J (2008) Modelling of fracture process in concrete using a novel lattice model. *Granular Matter* 10(5):377–388
17. Leclerc W, Haddad H, Guessasma M (2017) On the suitability of a Discrete Element Method to simulate cracks initiation and propagation in heterogeneous media. *International Journal of Solids and Structures* 108:98–114
18. O’Sullivan C (2011) Particulate discrete element modelling. A geomechanics perspective. Spon Press, Abingdon
19. Rojek J, Zubelewicz A, Madan N, Nosewicz S (2018) The discrete element method with deformable particles. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering* 114(8):828–860
20. Cosserat E, Cosserat F (1909) *Théorie des corps déformables*. Hermann, Paris
21. Nowacki W (1986) *Theory of asymmetric elasticity*. Pergamon, Oxford
22. Johnson GR, Cook WH (1983) A constitutive model and data for metals subjected to large strains, high strain rates and high temperatures. *Proceedings of the 7th International Symposium on Ballistics* 541–547
23. Chen X, Peng Y, Peng S, Yao S, Chen C, Xu P (2017) Flow and fracture behavior of aluminum alloy 6082-T6 at different tensile strain rates and triaxialities. *PLoS One* 12(7)
24. de Borst R (1993) A generalisation of J2-flow theory for polar continua. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* 103(3):347–362
25. Forest S, Sievert R (2003) Elastoviscoplastic constitutive frameworks for generalized continua. *Acta Mechanica* 160(1-2):71–111
26. Dietsche A, Steinmann P, Willam K (1993) Micropolar elastoplasticity and its role in localization. *International Journal of Plasticity* 9(7):813–831
27. Ortiz M, Simo JC (1986) An analysis of a new class of integration algorithms for elastoplastic constitutive relations. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering* 23:353–366

28. Šmilauer V, Catalano E, Chareyre B, Dorofeenko S, Duriez J, Dyck N, Eliáš J, Er B, Eulitz A, Gladky A, Guo N, Jakob C, Kneib F, Kozicki J, Marzougui D, Maurin R, Modenese C, Scholtès L, Sibille L, Stránský J, Sweijen T, Thoeni K, Yuan C (2015) Yade Documentation.
https://www.yade-dem.org/publi/documentation_2nd.ed/YadeBook.pdf. Cited 22 Mar 2023
29. Yan Z, Wilkinson SK, Stitt EH, Marigo M (2015) Discrete element modelling (DEM) input parameters: understanding their impact on model predictions using statistical analysis. *Computational Particle Mechanics* 2(3):283–299